

GENDER EQUALITY IS FUNDAMENTAL TO THE ACHIEVEMENT OF HUMAN RIGHTS

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Annotation: This article analyzes the universal advantages of gender equality have been well-documented, and several international frameworks have affirmed its centrality to human rights and sustainable development.

Key words: gender, international, frameworks, socially-constructed, gender equality, personal development.

Gender equality might mean that women and men should be treated equally, or differently. For example, it may imply that women and men should be paid the same for doing the same work or that they should be treated with different medicines and methods in order to make healthcare equal. Gender equality is a human right, but our world faces a persistent gap in access to opportunities and decision-making power for women and men. Gender equality means that men and women have equal power and equal opportunities for financial independence, education, and personal development.

The word gender describes the socially-constructed roles and responsibilities that societies consider appropriate for men and women. Gender equality means that men and women have equal power and equal opportunities for financial independence, education, and personal development. Women's empowerment is a critical aspect of achieving gender equality. It includes increasing a woman's sense of self-worth, her decision-making power, her access to opportunities and resources, her power and control over her own life inside and outside the home, and her ability to effect change. Yet gender issues are not focused on women alone, but on the relationship between men and women in society. The actions and attitudes of men and boys play an essential role in achieving gender equality.

Education is a key area of focus. Although the world is making progress in achieving gender parity in education, girls still make up a higher percentage of out-of-school children than boys. Approximately one quarter of girls in the developing world do not attend school. Typically, families with limited means who cannot afford costs such as school fees, uniforms, and supplies for all of their children will prioritize education for their sons. Families may also rely on girls' labor for household chores, carrying water, and childcare, leaving limited

time for schooling. But prioritizing girls' education provides perhaps the single highest return on investment in the developing world. An educated girl is more likely to postpone marriage, raise a smaller family, have healthier children, and send her own children to school. She has more opportunities to earn an income and to participate in political processes, and she is less likely to become infected with HIV. Women's health and safety is another important area. HIV/AIDS is becoming an increasingly impactful issue for women. This can be related to women having fewer opportunities for health education, unequal power in sexual partnership, or as a result of gender-based violence. Maternal health is also an issue of specific concern. In many countries, women have limited access to prenatal and infant care, and are more likely to experience complications during pregnancy and childbirth. This is a critical concern in countries where girls marry and have children before they are ready; often well before the age of 18. Quality maternal health care can provide an important entry point for information and services that empower mothers as informed decision-makers concerning their own health and the health of their children.

A final area of focus in attaining gender equality is women's economic and political empowerment. Though women comprise more than 50% of the world's population, they only own 1% of the world's wealth. Throughout the world, women and girls perform long hours of unpaid domestic work. In some places, women still lack rights to own land or to inherit property, obtain access to credit, earn income, or to move up in their workplace, free from job discrimination. At all levels, including at home and in the public arena, women are widely underrepresented as decision-makers. In legislatures around the world, women are outnumbered 4 to 1, yet women's political participation is crucial for achieving gender equality and genuine democracy.

In September 2019, Uzbekistan adopted the country's first ever gender equality law, "Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men". The long-awaited law represents a firm stance against gender-based discrimination and ensures equal rights for both sexes – an ambitious goal in a society with deeply-rooted gender stereotypes.

Even though the Constitution guarantees equal rights, opportunities for men and women still are far from equal. For example, women make up only 16 percent of the Legislative Chamber of Oliy Majlis (Parliament). Furthermore, women are under-represented in leadership positions, especially in the government, and are limited in their ability to own property or start a business. While there are no existing legal constraints, women also play a secondary role in science, research and technical areas, such as IT and engineering. Yet, there is

strong political will to change the status quo. With the USAID-funded Judicial Reform in Uzbekistan Program's support for the drafting process and public hearings, the government has declared a firm commitment to the country's first gender equality law. The law covers virtually all areas of life where discrimination is likely—political, economic, social, educational and familial—and clearly defines what gender-based discrimination is, and the legal actions that can be taken to counter it. As a result of this law, women's claims of discrimination can no longer be ignored on the basis of mentality or traditions.

Deputy Chairperson of the Oila Center under the Cabinet of Ministers, Ms. Gulnara Ishankhanova states, "The new law is an 'eye opener' for everybody, including the state, as it affirms that the state should not tolerate discrimination against women, even if it is founded on deeply engrained stereotypes. This law will prompt the state to evaluate each situation from a gender point of view, from hiring for jobs, improving higher education opportunities for women to resolving family disputes."

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